

Mongol Migration To Egypt And Bilad Al-Sham In Mamluk Era For The Period (658 - 694 AH/ 1260 - 1296 AD)

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Abstract

The study addresses Mongol migration during the period of AL-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars reign (658-676AH/ 1260-1277 AD) beside the sultan's perception and the his procedure's in dealing with Mongols, the search also presents the most significant migration during AL-Sultan Qalawn reign and his son AL-khalil(678-693AH/1279-1293AD) in addition the reasons behind the migration decreasing as compared with AL-ZaherBibars reign.

Introduction

The topic of Mongol migration to Egypt definitely in the state of navel Mamluk is considered as one of the most difficult and cross-cutting, the migrations had an effective role on the state and Mamluk community specially in politics, military and society. During the period (658-696AH/1260-1297AD), an important migration had taken place specially during the reign of Al-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars and Al-sultan Kitbugha and AL-Sultan received them and welcomed AL-Mogol warmly as a result, Mogol's migrations increased a matter rose AL-Sultan's fears and concerns of Mogol. Al-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars thought of Mogol increasing as a plan set up by his enemies, therefore, he put soldiers on alarm.

The research is divided into introduction, Two parts and conclusions. First part deals with Mogol migrations during the reign Al-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars and second part deals with Mogol's migration during the reign of Al-Sultan Qalawn and Al-Khalil (his son) reign finally the third part concerns with the migrations during the reign of Al-Sultan Kitbugha.

Firstly: Mongol's migration during the reign of AL-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars (658-676 AH/1260-1277 AD):

During Al-Sultan Bibars reign the first migrations has flocked to Egypt, many migrations (individual or group's) had been witnessed and Al-Sultan of Mamluk seemed to rely on Mongol in his army's formation, It can be argued that some factors increased migrations such as the good relationships among Mamluk, golden trips Mongol and Persian Mongol's which contributed in flocking Mongol in addition to the bad relationship between Persian Mongol's and their judges, some person Mongol's escaped and settled down in Egypt since it represented as a safe haven for their families.

IbnKatheer and AL-Maqrizi asserted the fact that, the initial Mongol migrations took place during the reign of AL-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars in 660AH/1262AD, IbnKatheer states that Tatar delegations arrived to Al-Sultan in hope find safety and Al-Sultan, by his role, honored them and was very generous supplying them efficient incomes. In the vein, AL-Maqrizi mentions these events by details and exposes the migrations, The king Baraka sent Mongol to stand with Holoqo but he ordered them Holoqo and Baraka Khan, had broken down and to informed to join the Egyptian military if they couldn't manage to join him.

AL-Sultan supported them and hosted them well in Bilad AL-Sham and later to Cairo there Al-Sultan by himself received them in (26 Thi AL-Hijja 660AH/21 November 1262 AD) and built them houses mating all their needs, horses, money. they almost were two hundred knights with their families, they got a good living and became muslims.

The Sultan's good reception and generosity attracted the other Mongol migrants. AL-Maqrizi indicated that Mongol groups flocked as a result of the sultan's generosity and good hospitality that led to increase Mongol's migrant numbers to Egypt obviously, the text above shows the main reasons behind Mongol influx which is due good hospitality and generosity consequently, many sects and Mongol groups were headed to Egypt, besides that it seemed that the sultan's desire to put migrants in his side and his military since they had great knowledge in military potential, moreover he wanted them to join Islam.

AL-Maqrizi mentioned that an arrival of new group in 661AH/ 1263AD who escaped from Al-Ilkhaian according to the Sultan Baraka Khan's order , Tattar arrived with their notables Qarmon , Amtakhia , Narkia , Jabric , Qian , Nasisa , Teshor , Nabto , Subhi , Jarjilan , Ajqarqa , Mutaqadim , The sultan rode his hours to meet them , as soon they saw him , They went down and kissed the ground under his feet , and he empored them , AL-Maqrizi states that , when The Sultan AL-ZaherBibars knew of migrants coming he celebrated and welcomed Them and did the same thing with the coming groups , He called them upon Islam and they accepted happily,Migration to Egypt continued for the above mentioned reasonsAL-Maqrizi indicated this events stating that influx came from Shiraz on the top of them , The prince Saif AL-DeenBiklik⁽ⁱ⁾ and much princes of Khafaja⁽ⁱⁱ⁾ they were received kindly by the sultan .

As the number of Mongol migrant raised the sultan got suspicious and afraid of these frequent migration , he viewed them as a part of policy set up by enemies , AL-Maqrizi said that many Barbarians and thieves arrived to Egypt so the sultan gathered princes to express his fears against these continuous migrations , then he came up with a decision , if Tattar obeyed rules then they would treated well and rewarded gift, horses and camels and money.

Al-Sultan AL-ZaherBibars crowed his son as a king to run to state affairs in his father absence` Al-Sultan never stopped his generosity with migrants , they lived in AL-Luoq on the limits of Cairo AL-Qalqashandi showed his hatred of Mongol saying that AL-Luoq was well built but badly inhabited by Barbarian

On 17thShawal 662 AH/12th of October 1264 AD , The Sultan informed of arrival another Mongol's trips so he ordered princes of Khafaja to behave generously with them .

As mentioned before , outlaws found Egypt as a safe haven not only civil people emigrated but significant figures in AL-Elikhanian state escaped from their judges like the prince Shams AL-DeenBahadir Three thousands migrants approached to Egypt during the reign of the Sultan Bibars , some of them were Khazakia (knights be longed to the sultan) and AL-Bira

Thus , the migrants of Mongol continued throughout the reign of the Sultan Bibars , IbnShadad said that the preparation of the Mongol coming to Egypt and Bilad AL-Sham daring his era of about three thousands same^l . AL-Maqrizi said that saying the magnifying of the Mongol in the reign of the Sultan AL-ZaherBibars , there was copied Egypt and Bilad AL-Sham .

It's notable that the increasing of Mongol numbers let to overcrowding in AL-Luoq area in Cairo which considered as their in habitat , Therefore sultan ordered to build them houses inside castlethat are known as ruins of Tattars⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾, It's essential to note that the Sultan AL-ZaherBibars was very keen to isolate the groups in special places , and this due to the fact that AL-Mamalik always felt alienated in the state of Egyptian and Bilad AL-Sham , They were conscious of the differences between them , there for they lived as a stranger^(iv) .

Maybe you come to mind some of the questions , Why did The sultan choose AL-Luoq in specific ? The answer is related to the geographic position of this city.

The sultan needed militant groups in the coastal area and Al Ing was the best to pace any external aggression

Secondly : Migration of Mongol during the rule of the Sultan AL-Mansur Qalawon and his son AL-Ashraf Khalil (678-693AH /1279-1293 AD) :

During the reign of The Sultan Al-Mansur Qalawon , a significant decrease in migration was witnessed as compared with AL-ZaherBirbas reign, never the less , migration never stopped at that time , sincemany unrests had been accursed in the state period of Ahmed Takwdar reign and his nephew attempt to change the government , all these factors effected badly on the economic of the country a matter forced Mongol to run away.

Regarding the period of the Sultan AL-Ashraf Khalil reign , Mongol migration decreased , only two hundred migrant arrived to Egypt, The sultan recieved them and empowered them, the reasons of immigration still ambiguous , yet .

It may be due to the judge's in justice mismanagement besides an economic factors that had effected badly on people..

Finally :

It had been argued that the period of The Sultan Bibars was completely full of Mongol migrants to Egypt and Bilad AL-Sham , some sources asserts that three thousands migrants arrived to Egypt and this due to the good hospitality, on the other hand the period (678_693AH/1274_1293AD) had witnessed a great decreasing of migration and the reason of that due to the important of Bilad AL-Sham condition during the reign of Ahmed Takodar beside the truce with Mongol .

References

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 AL-Nowairi , Nihayat AL-Erb , section 30 , p63 ; IbnAebik AL-Dawadari , Kanz AL-Durar , section8 ,
 p.p 90-91 .
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 IbnShadad , History of King AL-Zaher , p.p337-338 .
 AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section 1 , p561 . And see too IbnAbd Al-zaher , AL-RawdAlzaher , p137 ; Bibars
 AL-Mansuri , zubdat AL-Fikra , p 84-85 ; AL-Nowairi , Nihayat AL-Erb , section 31 , p38 ; ALthahabi ,
 History of Islam , section 49 , p 8 ; AL-Yafuaai , ThailMeraatALzaman , section 4 , p121 .
 AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section1 , p561 . And see too Al-Yonini ,ThailMeraat AL-Zaman , section 2 , p195
 .Shiraz : It's an ancient city in the western south of BiladFaris , Mohammed Ibn Al-khasimreput it by the
 time of the Islamic conquest (695AH/713AD) , Shiraz means a hollow of lion. when the Islamic military
 arrived to BiladFaris , they dewlt in that place and settled there till Astakhar city established , MuslIms
 were pleased with this place and built Shiraz . the city was valuable , well improved , it was full of
 binding , there were no walls , markets, houses had big garden of fruits . Yaqut AL-Hamawi
 ,MuaajamALBoldan , section3 , p 381 ; AL-Humairy , ALRawd AL-Zahir , p351 .
 (Saif AL-DeenBiklik , he was one of the Mogol princes who arrived to Egypt during the reign of The sultan
 Bibars, The sultan anpowered him and crowned him as a prince of AL-Tabilkhanat in Cairo . AL-
 Nowairi , Nihayat AL-Erb , section 30 , p99 ; AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section2 , p 8 .
 (Khafaja : It's one of the most important trip of AkeelIbnKab Bin Amir Bin Saasaan . Their name comes from
 their grandfather Khafaja Bin Amro Bin Akeen Bin kaab .Orginally they were an Iraqi princes inhabited
 Heat and AL-Anbar till Nakhla and Kufa . The most prominent figures of this trips are Klider Bin Badran
 Bin Muqalid Bin Suluman Bin Mharish AL-Ebadi ,Shahir Bin Ahmed AL-Khafagi .IbnFadlullah AL
 Omari , Msalik AL Absar , section 4 , p.p351-352 ; Al-Qalqashandi , Nehayat AL-Erb Fe MaarifatAnsab
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 AL-Luoq : Linguistically , in Arabic languages AL-Luoq means soften things. It located in the front part of
 Cairo. The ground of this city was fertile a since water of Nile had receded there . Al-Qalqashandi ,
 Suboh AL-Aasha , section3 , p408 ; AL-Maqrizi , Al-Khutut , section3 , p210 ; Dahman , Muaajam AL-
 Alfaz AL-Tarikhia , p133 .
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 AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section2 , p11 .
 The prince Shams AL-DeenBahiderIbnFaraj bin Abdulla Sahib Samisat , The
 prince arrived to Cairo in (672AH/1274AD) and the sultan Bibars empowered him, he stayed in Cairo
 till his death in (676AH/1278AD) . IbnTahgriBardy , AL-Dalil AL-Shafi , section1 , p199 .
 AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section2 , p86 ; AL-Nowairi , Nehayat AL-Erb , section30 , p207 .
 AL-Maqrizi , AL-Siluok , section2 , p86 .
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 AL Maqrizi , AL Siluok , section2 , p49 .
 The same source , section2 , p165 .
 IbnKatheer , Start and end , section14 , p40 .

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